

Evaluation of ground water quality in Amarpatan, Sohawal, and Majhgawan tahsils in Satna District Madhya Pradesh.

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Abstract

The current study examines the subterranean water quality of a few specific regions in Satna District using specific Total hardness, TDS, BOD, NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , Cl^- , F^- , HCO_3^- , Mg^{++} , K^+ , Alkalinity, *E.coli*. and Alge. nitrate and sulphate were carried out in the month of march-2021 by using standard methods. It was observed that underground water quality in selected area is not bad for drinking, domestic and agriculture purposes. This study also express seasonal variation of water quality and slight increment in some selected parameters were observed when data of pre monsoon and post monsoon compared. It indicates that some parameter may cross maximum contamination level in next upcoming years. areas, Underground water, all chemical, electrical conductivity, total hardness, Alkalinity.

Key words: Water, Earth, TDS, BOD, NO_3

Introduction: -

One of the most vital substances for the upkeep of life is natural water. The ancient Greek philosopher Thales of Miletus described it as "a primary source of all that exist" 2,600 years ago. One of the most amazing substances on the planet, water is still a mystery to science today. It differs greatly from other substances due to a variety of anomalous qualities (such as high melting, boiling, and evaporation temperatures, and dissolving ability). The hydrosphere, which is not the Earth's continuous water cover, contains the majority of the planet's water. By volume, the hydrosphere is made up of subsurface waters in 2.32 percent and oceans and seas in approximately 84.2 percent.

The hydrosphere, which is not the Earth's continuous water cover, contains the majority of the planet's water. Protective measures should be taken to check water pollution because the results clearly show that the water in the studied area is not highly contaminated. However, the concentration of the various parameters is trending towards the higher side, indicating an increasing level of water pollution. This could be caused by the discharge of industrial effluents on land and surface water bodies. The chemistry of the groundwater is largely dependent on this. In the world, both rural and urban communities have relied heavily on groundwater as a source of drinking water.

All water masses are transformed from one to another in the course of the hydrological cycle, a continual shift of water on the Earth that occurs under the influence of solar radiation and gravity (M. G. Khublaryan -1991). The main expressed problems affecting water quality and aquatic ecosystems were untreated domestic sewage, uncontrolled industrial discharges, deforestation and poor agricultural practices that result in soil erosion and leaching of nutrients and pesticides. During its 6th session in 1998.

Material and Methods-

Selection of sample sites:

Satna District run for Agriculture Sector and Industry area logiest region my research side of various sides of Satna District. The research area's sampling stations were selected at various locations, and water samples were gathered from the Satna district's residential and industrial

areas. A sample of water was collected in sterile plastic bottles for testing. The number of farmers in the Amarpatan tehsil of Satna district was discovered, and it was noted that any water used in this tehsil - for irrigation or agricultural promotion—is not completely purified by river wells through boreholes, or that when we irrigate, we should consider the same factors as parameter, TS, TDS BOD, and other things that can be irrigated in people run for Agriculture land primarily in several Satna areas. The agricultural practices of the farmers in the village are notably distinct and mostly influenced by the irrigation phase. Though because of their, farmers and vegetable producers in the region try to imitate the irrigation water supplied by them.

Then same condition of Kothi and Majhgawan are same direction Areas of farmers in the Satna district's Amarpatan tehsil was found, and it was observed that any water used in this tehsil—for irrigation or agricultural promotion—is not entirely purified by river wells through boreholes, or that factors like parameter, pH, EC, TH, Temperature, and other things that can be irrigated in all people should be taken into consideration when we irrigate mostly in a few Satna regions. The irrigation phase has a major influence on the farmers' agricultural techniques, which are noticeably different throughout the community. The district's farmers and vegetable growers try to duplicate the irrigation water they supply, however because of them.

To prevent any unforeseen changes in the physic-chemical features, the sample bottles were rapidly transferred to the laboratory after being securely sealed after collection. Below is Table 1 with all of the sampling locations displayed. A survey was carried out in the months of April through June. The following sample sites in the Satna region were chosen for this study based on a review of the literature. Only those locations were picked where no such study has ever been conducted before. Samples were gathered in the pre-, during, and post-monsoon periods.

Analysis of water samples:

Pre-, man-, and post-monsoon water sample collection was conducted in 2021 using pre-selected sampling sites and 250 ml polypropylene bottles. Water samples were subjected to standard procedures as outlined in John Sistosha (2016) for analysis based on selected parameters, including PH, temperature, electrical conductivity, total hardness, TDS, BOD, NO₃⁻, SO₄⁻², PO₄⁻³, Cl⁻, F⁻, HCO₃⁻, Mg⁺⁺, K⁺, alkalinity, E. coli, and algae. The pH scale has a range of 6.35 to 7.41. A high pH is linked to inorganic acid or a trace amount of mineral acid from carbonate sources. The lowest value is 7.41, and the maximum value is 5.71.

Table 1: Selected area for sample collection in each tahsils in Satna District.

S. N.	Selected Area and Sample sites		Type of water source	Use	Code
1	Amarpatan	Govt. H.S. School	Bore well	Public	AP1
		P.H. C.	Bore well	Public	AP2
		Tahsil HQ	Hand pipe	Public	AP3
2-	Ramnagar	Govt. H.S. School	Bore well	Public	RN1
		P.H. C.	Bore well	Public	RN2
		Tahsil HQ	Bore well	Public	RN3
3-	Nagod	Govt. H.S. School	Handpipe	Public	ND1
		P.H. C.	Bore well	Public	ND2
		Tahsil HQ	Bore well	Public	ND3
4-	Majhgawan	Govt. H.S. School	Bore well	Public	RJ1
		P.H. C.	Bore well	Public	RJ2
		Tahsil HQ	Bore well	Public	RJ3
5-	Sohawal	Govt. H.S. School	Bore well	Public	SL1
		P.H. C.	Handpipe	Public	SL2
		Tahsil HQ	Bore well	Public	SL3
6-	Rampur Baghelan	Govt. H.S. School	Bore well	Public	RB1
		P.H. C.	Bore well	Public	RB2
		Tahsil HQ	Bore well	Public	RB3
7-	Unchehara	Govt. H.S. School	Bore well	Public	UA1
		P.H. C.	Bore well	Public	UA2
		Tahsil HQ	Bore well	Public	UA3
8-	Maihar	Govt. H.S. School	Bore well	Public	MH1
		P.H. C.	Bore well	Public	MH2
		Tahsil HQ	Bore well	Public	MH3

Result and discussion:-

I collected a sample of water from various locations and tehsils, and I tested the water in the pollution control board for five days straight in each sample to determine the water's acidity, lopsidedness, and intensity. We would be dealing with subterranean water problems today if we did not discuss rain and water; otherwise, the water would not be drinkable. Tables 2, 3, and 4 present the findings for the chosen parameters for the pre-, during-, and post-monsoon periods. At all sampling sites, the PH was found to be within permissible limits and to vary between 6.5 and 7.7. The maximum PH was measured during the monsoon, whereas the lowest value was found

before and after TDS, BOD, NO₃⁻, SO₄⁻², PO₄⁻³, Cl⁻, F⁻, HCO₃⁻, Mg⁺⁺, K⁺, Alkalinity, E. Coli, and Alge. The number of farmers in the Amarpatan tehsil of the Satna district was determined, and it was noted that any water used in this tehsil for irrigation or agricultural promotion is not completely purified by river wells through boreholes, or that when we irrigate, we should take into consideration things like parameter, STTS TDS bode, and other things that can be irrigated in Krishna primarily in a few Satna areas. The community's farmers use distinctly varied agricultural techniques, much of which may be attributed to the irrigation phase. Farmers and vegetable growers in the area attempt to replicate the irrigation water they provide, however due to them. The number of farmers in Satna district's Amarpatan Tehsil.

Table 2: Analysis of water samples- The following parameters were used to analyze the water samples.

Sample Site Code	April 2021 (Pre monsoon)																
	Parameters																
	pH	EC Micro S/cm	TH ppm	TDS ppm	BOD 5day	TEMP °C	NO3-Mg/L	ALKALINITY ppm	K+ ppm	PO4-3 ppm	Cl ppm	SO4 ppm	F Mg/L	HCO3	Mg	<i>E.coli</i> MPN/100	Alge
AP1	6.8	873	218	640	3.1	29.9	2.15	164	42	1.32	35	150	1	123	64	1	ND
AP2	5.9	852	214	635	2.9	28.8	4.35	175	40	2.52	33	138	0.9	132	59	1	ND
AP3	6.9	867	219	642	3.3	30.7	2.11	170	45	1.43	29	138	1.1	129	68	1.1	ND
RN1	7.1	866	212	640	2.9	29.2	4.64	161	42	2.68	34	139	1	139	66	0.9	ND
RN2	6.7	853	216	636	2.7	29.8	4.52	160	43	2.41	36	137	1	131	67	0.9	ND
RN3	6.5	829	219	631	2.8	29.5	3.04	149	42	2.19	33	147	1.1	137	65	1	ND
ND1	6.7	842	262	627	2.9	30.5	4.31	162	41	2.32	32	138	1	130	63	0.8	ND
ND2	7	835	247	629	2.8	30	4.2	153	41	2.52	29	142	1.1	129	66	1	ND
ND3	6.9	848	246	641	2.7	30.1	4.44	169	43	2.57	34	134	1	136	62	1	ND
RJ1	7.1	843	237	631	2.9	30.4	1.91	171	40	1.61	33	128	1.1	138	63	1.2	ND
RJ2	6.5	840	245	649	2.8	29.1	4.61	157	41	2.52	33	140	1	139	67	1	ND
RJ3	7	833	241	645	2.7	29.8	3.97	171	43	2.65	31	133	1	129	66	0.8	ND
SL1	6.9	836	238	634	2.6	30.7	3.82	162	46	1.93	32	128	1.1	137	65	1	ND
SL2	5.9	832	249	629	2.3	30.3	4.32	151	47	2.18	37	127	0.9	130	68	1	ND
SL3	5.8	843	247	638	2.4	29.5	4.1	168	42	2.07	36	128	0.8	138	66	1.1	ND
RB1	6.1	845	245	646	2.9	30.8	3.88	171	39	1.96	38	138	1	127	65	1.2	ND
RB2	6.3	836	237	641	3.3	30.2	4.32	149	40	2.18	33	142	1	138	63	1.3	ND
RB3	6.7	818	249	640	3.5	31	1.93	170	43	0.98	35	138	1.2	130	64	1.1	ND
UA1	6.4	846	246	638	2.6	32.3	4.25	151	42	2.14	31	128	1.2	132	66	1.1	ND
UA2	5.8	845	243	635	2.5	31.1	4.64	166	42	2.34	33	127	1.1	139	65	0.8	ND
UA3	7.2	840	242	633	2.9	30.5	1.84	159	41	0.94	34	133	0.8	139	67	0.9	ND
MH1	6.6	862	248	636	3	30.9	2.71	153	46	1.37	36	135	1	134	65	1.1	ND
MH2	6.8	863	247	642	3.1	30.3	4.62	160	48	2.33	35	142	0.9	129	65	1.2	ND
MH3	6.6	856	244	638	3.4	30	4.54	154	46	2.29	36	134	0.9	137	64	1.2	ND

Fig.1: The following parameters were used to analyze the water samples.

Table 3: Analysis of water samples- Water samples were analysed on the basis of following parameters.

Sample Site Code	July 2021 (monsoon)																
	Parameters																
	PH	EC MicroS/cm	TH ppm	TDS ppm	BOD 5day	TE Mp °C	NO3-Mg/L	ALKALINITY ppm	K+ ppm	PO4-3 ppm	Cl ppm	SO4 ppm	F Mg/L	HCO3	Mg	E.coli MPN/100	Alge
AP1	6.3	856	222	648	3.4	30.3	4.78	162	45	2.34	33	135	0.9	145	67	1	ND
AP2	6.5	855	233	644	2.8	30.4	4.49	169	46	2.43	36	129	0.7	136	66	1.1	ND
AP3	6.4	862	234	642	3.3	31.1	4.7	156	43	1.93	36	126	0.8	142	65	1	ND
RN1	6.6	864	235	640	3.1	29.5	4.61	160	42	2.34	35	130	0.9	146	66	ND	ND
RN2	6.7	863	219	634	3.6	30.2	4.79	159	43	2.04	42	132	0.8	128	68	ND	ND
RN3	6	866	223	636	3	30.3	4.97	170	45	2.03	41	128	0.7	130	63	1	ND
ND1	6.5	868	242	635	3.5	30.5	3.88	161	40	2.19	36	121	0.9	146	65	0.9	ND
ND2	6.5	852	249	634	3.3	30.2	4.79	172	38	2.34	33	133	0.8	131	67	1	ND
ND3	6.3	856	235	637	3	30	4.19	165	39	1.93	31	127	0.8	148	65	1.1	ND
RJ1	6.6	864	237	635	3.6	29.8	4.1	169	45	2.33	36	126	0.7	136	60	0.9	ND
RJ2	6.5	861	244	645	2.9	29.2	4.49	170	46	2.05	28	125	0.9	145	67	ND	ND
RJ3	6.4	855	245	644	2.6	30.4	4.79	161	44	2	35	134	0.8	131	64	0.9	ND
SL1	6.4	866	243	635	3.6	31.5	3.98	160	47	2.19	34	133	0.8	134	63	1.1	ND
SL2	6.6	867	247	640	2.6	30.2	4.77	169	46	2.04	36	121	0.9	139	66	ND	ND
SL3	6.5	866	246	644	2.5	30.8	4.22	161	44	2	38	126	0.7	146	68	1	ND
RB1	6.4	856	243	642	2.7	30.5	4.12	165	46	2.19	35	133	0.9	136	67	0.9	ND
RB2	6.5	855	248	638	3	30.2	4.49	168	44	0.95	28	135	0.6	139	66	1.1	ND
RB3	6	865	246	637	3.4	30.8	4.2	167	44	2	33	129	0.9	138	65	1	ND
UA1	6.5	852	245	645	3.6	31.9	4.11	157	41	1.98	31	130	0.7	148	65	ND	ND
UA2	6.5	856	243	644	2.5	29.5	4.49	159	46	2.34	37	136	0.8	139	66	ND	ND
UA3	6.6	865	246	635	2.7	30.3	2.01	160	45	2.43	36	132	0.7	137	68	1	ND
MH1	6.5	866	247	632	2.8	30.9	4.11	165	40	1.93	34	131	0.9	134	63	ND	ND
MH2	6	864	246	636	3.6	30.5	4.08	169	46	2.34	35	134	0.8	131	64	1.1	ND
MH3	6.5	867	246	645	3.1	30.5	4.63	164	48	2.1	34	116	0.7	142	65	0.9	ND

Fig. 2: Analysis of water samples- Water samples were analyzed on the basis of following parameters.

Table 4: Analysis of water samples- water samples were analyzed on the basis of following parameters:

Sample Site Code	November 2021 (Post Monsoon)																
	Parameters																
	PH	EC Mic roS/ cm	TH ppm	TDS ppm	BOD 5day	TEM p °C	NO3- Mg/L	ALKALI NITY Ppm	K+ pp m	PO4 -3 Ppm	Cl ppm	SO4 Ppm	F Mg/ L	HCO 3	Mg	E.coli MPN/10 0	Alge
AP1	6.3	866	217	643	3	27	4.68	172	43	2.29	36	117	0.9	141	64	1.1	ND
AP2	5.6	857	214	636	2.9	26.9	4.41	187	38	2.15	34	84	0.7	142	60	0.9	ND
AP3	6.3	868	212	643	3.4	28.2	4.76	182	39	2.33	34	120	0.8	135	67	1.0	ND
RN1	6.6	865	215	640	3.2	26.4	2.68	179	42	1.29	35	111	0.9	129	65	ND	ND
RN2	6.1	862	214	637	3.6	27.6	3.96	183	45	1.93	32	98	0.7	145	66	1.0	ND
RN3	5.9	837	216	636	3.1	26.8	4.06	189	41	1.98	29	116	0.9	133	64	ND	ND
ND1	6.7	839	243	634	3.7	26.7	1.87	171	40	0.88	36	116	0.9	139	62	0.9	ND
ND2	6.5	839	245	633	2.8	27	3.03	176	37	1.46	35	104	0.8	146	66	1.0	ND
ND3	6.3	853	244	637	3.1	27.1	4.66	171	47	2.28	33	115	0.7	136	65	0.9	ND
RJ1	6.6	840	236	636	3.6	27.9	4.69	179	45	2.29	34	117	0.6	138	62	1.1	ND
RJ2	6	839	241	646	3.8	26	3.59	173	46	1.74	37	112	0.9	135	65	1.0	ND
RJ3	6.5	836	240	648	3.7	27.6	2.29	197	44	1.09	36	98	0.8	143	68	0.9	ND
SL1	6.7	834	236	649	2.6	28.8	3.05	185	42	1.47	35	120	0.6	137	63	0.8	ND
SL2	5.6	837	245	636	2.6	27.9	4.66	171	45	2.28	37	126	0.7	123	67	ND	ND
SL3	5.7	845	247	640	2.8	26.3	4.75	186	42	2.32	34	106	0.8	140	64	1.0	ND
RB1	5.5	848	246	645	2.9	28.5	3.55	190	46	1.72	37	94	0.9	146	68	1.1	ND
RB2	5.8	839	243	643	3.7	27.6	4.35	195	45	2.12	38	88	0.7	144	65	1.2	ND
RB3	6.2	832	247	641	3.6	28.9	4.56	182	41	2.23	34	104	0.9	138	66	ND	ND
UA1	5.9	848	247	647	2.5	27.6	3.96	198	47	1.93	33	110	0.8	136	64	0.8	ND
UA2	5.3	841	240	639	2.8	27.7	4.75	173	46	2.32	35	106	0.8	137	65	0.9	ND
UA3	6.4	843	239	636	2.9	28.5	2.85	171	48	1.37	36	108	0.7	148	66	ND	ND
MH1	6.2	858	245	635	3.3	28.9	3.96	196	45	1.93	34	94	0.8	140	64	1.0	ND
MH2	6.3	859	246	643	3.4	26.6	4.66	186	47	2.28	35	116	0.7	129	63	1.1	ND
MH3	6.1	856	243	640	3.7	27.4	4.57	196	44	2.23	37	89	0.6	144	67	ND	ND

Fig. 3: Analysis of water samples- water samples were analyzed on the basis of following parameters:

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